

Release Note : v1.1-alpha

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1 Introduction and Overview

This release note contains information about the changes made to a BBiCat software and what functionalities can be found. Throughout the text, classes and packages where specific tools can be found will be mentioned. Current release of the software contains simple Bi-clustering routines, Bayesian analytics for term enrichment, and relevant parsers and translation tools.

2 BicAT GUI

Software package contains a simple Graphical User Interface (GUI) provided as part of the BicAT toolbox (Barkow & Zitzler, 2006) which can be used in order to perform the biclustering on a loaded dataset. Some examples of the sample datasets are included in the *sampleData* folder. One important factor to take into account about the GUI element is the architecture under which algorithm libraries were compiled. Some of the methods were distributed by the original developers as native libraries. These libraries were compiled

under the 32-bit architecture, leading to a incompatibility with the 64-bit Java Runtime Environment (JRE). This means that if GUI element is being used, JRE used for a run should be switched to a 32-bit alternative.

BicAT GUI, thus, is not always able to deal with the datasets of a larger size. Current work tries to integrate locally implemented BiMax (Prelic et al., 2006) method into GUI. This integration would solve the architecture incompatibility problems. However, in order to be able to make use of the 64-bit architectures that most of the latest laptops and machines have, one has to implement all the provided (Bi)Clustering techniques found in the BicAT toolbox. This contains Iterative Signature Algorithm (ISA) (Ihmels & Barkai, 2004), xMotifs (Murali & Kasif, 2003), Cheng and Church (CC) (Cheng & Church, 2000) and Order Preserving Sub-Matrix (OPSM) method (Ben-Dor, 2003). Thus, BicAT GUI still requires the 32-bit JRE.

Fig. 2.1: Overview of BicAT GUI

3 Biclustering Methods

As already mentioned, all the biclustering and clustering techniques were distributed as being native libraries (.dll files) as part of the BicAT toolbox (Barkow & Zitzler, 2006). Among these methods, of utter most interest for a time being was the BiMax (Prelic et al., 2006) algorithm. One of the first goals of a project was to assess the performance and quality of the results obtained from BiMax, both from numeric and biological perspective. That is why in the first release, only the local implementation of this algorithm is included. Implementation can be found under *bicat/biclustering* package. Implementation is a Java adaptation of a C code written originally by Eckart Zitzler. For code to work, binary matrix should be fed in to the class.

Possible usage of this class is shown in the *MyBiMaxTest.java* file which can be found under the *MetaFramework/TestCases* package. Additionally, when the biclusters are registered in the software, their Mean Squared Residue Score (MSRS) value is automatically computed. This measure represents a numeric value of bicluster homogeneity. MSRS, by itself, is a valuable quality metric. However it does not include any domain knowledge in its computation. This leads to a next step of cluster analysis: Analysing how fitting are the results with the knowledge we already have about the parts of different systems (*-omics* data)

4 Post-Analysis tools

As already mentioned, for further assessment of the clustering techniques, natural next step was to analyse how fitting are the obtained clusters with the

biological knowledge domains available to public. For this purpose, a parser was implemented in order to deal with the the NCI - Nature Curated Pathway Interaction Database (Carl F. Schaefer, Buetow, et al., 2009). NCI database contains list of molecules, interactions that connect the molecules among each other and pathways, which are represented as being list of interactions. Parser for this database can be found under the *MetaFramework* package under the name of *PathwayAnalysisMixing.java*. Future releases will contain parsers for Gene Ontology (GO) terms, KEGG pathways and many other *-omics* databases.

An alternative for performing post-analysis on obtained clusters is the term enrichment analysis. Term enrichment analysis tries to highlight the biological terms that are either over or under-represented in a given set of genes. There are many Frequentist tests available that can be used for term enrichment analysis. However, they tend to focus only on the significance analysis, thus ignoring the statistical association between terms/pathways and molecules. One possible approach of including the statistical association in the analysis is to use the Bayesian analysis of ontology term enrichment. This technique is outlined in (Ricardo Z.N. Vencio & Carlos A. de B., 2006). Implementation of a Bayesian Analysis can be found in *MetaFramework* package under the name of *Bayesian.java*.

Additionally, there are some routines included that connects R and Java programming languages in order to go through some databases easily available in R. However, this approach is not integrated into Bayesian analysis yet.

5 Translation tools

Molecules are mainly represented with their HGNC Symbol names in NCI Database. Unfortunately, different dataset and databases encode genes/molecules in different conventions. These conventions may include Illumicodes, Entrez ID and many others. As this project's main focus is the analysis of Twin-sUK dataset (Grundberg, Small, et al., 2012), where molecules/parts are represented with their Illumina codes, a translation tool is implemented for mapping molecules from their Illumicodes to their HGNC Symbols. *IlluminaParsers.java* class is the implementation of this translation tool.

Possible extension of this translation tool is already included in the first release. *TranslationScript.R* file contains an R script which can retrieve HGNC Symbol names of a given gene names from a given convention. Possible use of this script as part of a Java code is demonstrated in *TranslationEngineTest.java*.

6 Summary

First alpha release of the BBiCat software, v1.1-alpha, already includes tools that can be used for mashing together biclustering techniques, Bayesian term enrichment analysis and translation of genes from a given domain to HGNC Symbols. This release is intended as being a basis for further developments and proof-of-concept experimentations.

7 Contact

If needed, maintainer (Taghi Aliyev) can be contacted at taghi.aliyev@cern.ch.

8 Citing

You can cite the alpha-release of the software. DOI for citing is : 10.5281/zenodo.33149 . Additionally, the software release can be cited as:

Aliyev, Taghi et al.. (2015). BBiCat: Alpha version of a Java Implementation of BBiCat project. Zenodo. 10.5281/zenodo.33149

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